

A Micromechanics Method to Predict the Fracture Toughness of Carbon Foam

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SUMMARY: Single edge-notched four-point bending tests were conducted in order to predict the Mode I fracture toughness of open cell carbon foam. In addition to the experimental approach, finite element based micromechanical methods have been developed to predict the fracture toughness. A micromechanical model was developed assuming a rectangular prism as the unit-cell. A small region surrounding the crack tip was modeled with three-dimensional solid elements and it was subjected to boundary displacements (u_x and u_y) corresponding to a unit stress intensity factor K_I , i.e., $K_I = 1$. Displacements were applied to the boundary of the region based on linear elastic fracture mechanics for orthotropic materials. From the finite element results, the Mode I stress intensity factor that causes failure of a crack tip element was determined and it was taken as the fracture toughness of the foam. A simpler model in which the foam was composed of struts of square cross section was also considered. The micromechanical simulations were performed to study the variation of fracture toughness as a function of foam density. Good agreement was found between the finite element and experimental results for fracture toughness of carbon foam. The results indicate that micromechanics can be a useful tool to study crack propagation and predict the fracture toughness of cellular materials such as carbon foam.

KEYWORDS: *carbon foam, cellular solids, finite element method, fracture toughness, micro-mechanics*

INTRODUCTION

Cellular materials are made up of network of beam/plate like structures leaving an open space or cell in between. Cellular materials, e.g., carbon, offer several advantages such as thermal resistance, durability, low density, impact damage tolerance and cost effectiveness. They have great potential as core materials for sandwich construction, heat exchangers and thermal protection systems in the military and commercial aerospace structures. Some of the applications of carbon foam are in heat exchangers and thermal protection systems. An excellent treatise on the structure and properties of cellular solids has been written by Gibson and Ashby [1]. While analytical methods for determining the thermal and mechanical properties of carbon foam are well documented, research on fracture behavior of various foams is still at infancy. Gibson and Ashby [1] have presented approximate formulas for Mode I fracture toughness of cellular solids in terms of their relative density and tensile strength. These are limited to cracks parallel to the principal material direction. Choi and Sankar [2] have developed FE based micromechanics to predict the fracture toughness of cellular solids under Mode I, Mode II and mixed mode conditions. Further, they have studied fracture toughness in various crack angles to the principal material direction. In the present study the Mode I fracture toughness of carbon foam was measured using single edge notched bend specimen. A finite element method based on micro-mechanics has been developed to predict the fracture toughness. The agreement between the experimental and numerical results is good indicating micro-mechanics can be a powerful tool in predicting the fracture behavior of foams and other cellular solids.

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A SEM was used to capture the images of carbon foam as shown in Fig. 1. In microscopic observation, the open-cells are irregularly sized and spaced. The cell size is measured to be in the range of 1 to 2 mm. Mechanical properties of the carbon foam are shown in Table 1. The solidity (relative density) is determined by dividing, ρ^* , density of the foam, by ρ_s , the density of solid carbon that make the struts or the cell walls. The densities of various forms of carbon are given in Table 2. The solidity of the carbon foam used in the present study was based on the value of $\rho_s = 2,250 \text{ kg/m}^3$, and it is determined as 0.1312.

Fig. 1 SEM images of low (left) and high (right) density carbon foam

Table 1 Mechanical properties of carbon foam

Elastic Modulus (E^*)	123.79 MPa
Tensile strength (σ_u^*)	3.5805 MPa
Density (ρ^*)	295.3 kg/m^3

Table 2 Densities of various forms of carbon

Diamond (C Wt. %100)	3,510 kg/m^3
Graphite carbon fiber (C Wt. %100)	2,250 kg/m^3
Zoltec Pane 30MF carbon fiber (C Wt. % 99.5)	1,750 kg/m^3

FRACTURE TESTS

There are several methods to measure the fracture toughness of cellular materials. Compact tension test (CT), Single edge notched bend test (SENB) and Double edge notched tension test (DENT) performed by Fowlkes [3] are some of the tests that are suitable for foam materials. In the present study, we chose the single edge notched four-point bend specimens for measuring the fracture toughness of carbon foams.

Fig. 2 SENB Specimen geometry

It was thought that the four-point bending test would yield more accurate and repeatable results as the crack is in a region under constant bending moment and there is no shear force present. Further, small offset of the loading with respect to the crack location will not significantly affect the results. The specimen dimensions are shown in Fig. 2. Individual specimen dimensions are given in Table 3. The height of the specimen was about 50 mm and the crack length was about 25 mm. A notch was cut using a diamond saw, and a razor blade was used to sharpen the crack tip. The crack length was the distance of the crack tip from the edge of the beam. The tests were conducted under displacement control in a material-testing machine at the rate of 0.5 mm/min (Fig. 3). The load-deflection behavior is linear before the specimens fail in a brittle manner (Fig. 4). The fracture loads for various specimens are listed in Table 3. The Mode I fracture toughness was calculated from the load at failure using the following formula [4]:

$$K_I = \sigma_\infty \sqrt{\pi a} \left(1.12 - 1.39 \frac{a}{w} + 7.3 \frac{a^2}{w^2} - 13 \frac{a^3}{w^3} + 14 \frac{a^4}{w^4} \right) \quad \text{Eqn. 1}$$

where the maximum bending stress σ_∞ is determined by

$$\sigma_\infty = \frac{M \bar{y}}{I} = \frac{M \frac{w}{2}}{B \frac{w^3}{12}} = \frac{6M}{Bw^2} \quad \text{Eqn. 2}$$

Fig. 3 four-point bending test setup on a material testing machine

In Eqn. 2, M is the constant bending moment in the central region, h is the height of the specimen and B is the width. The bending moment M is given by $M=Pd/2$, where d is distance between one of the top loading points and the corresponding bottom support as shown in Fig. 2. The results for fracture toughness are listed in Table 3. For the carbon foam samples tested the average Mode I fracture toughness is found to be $0.1337 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ with a standard deviation of $0.011 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ (about 8%).

Fig. 4 Load-displacement curves of point bending tests on carbon foam

Table 3 Fracture toughness with specimen properties of carbon foam

Specimen	Span L (m)	Height h (m)	Width B (m)	Crack length a (m)	Density (Kg/m ³)	Fracture Load (N)	K_{Ic} (MPa m ^{1/2})
IF06	0.2284	0.0512	0.0255	0.0264	284	100.9	0.1315
IF07	0.2291	0.0500	0.0255	0.0252	301	112.0	0.1458
IF09	0.2290	0.0507	0.0255	0.0259	292	92.54	0.1201
IF10	0.2290	0.0506	0.0256	0.0261	297	105.8	0.1372

FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATIONS

Unit-Cell Model and Solid Properties: The first step in simulating the crack propagation in carbon foam is to idealize the microstructure of the foam. The unit-cell is assumed as a perfect cube. The foam is simulated by placing a spherical void (bubble) at the center of the cube (Fig. 5). By varying the radius of the bubble, foams of various solidity can be modeled.

Fig. 5 Unit cell of beam (left) and solid models (right)

A relation between the solidity and the R/c ratio can be derived [2] as:

$$\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} = \frac{4 + \pi}{4} + \frac{8}{3}\pi\left(\frac{R}{c}\right)^3 - 3\pi\left(\frac{R}{c}\right)^2, \quad \frac{1}{2} < \frac{R}{c} < \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$$

Eqn. 3

The average dimension of the unit-cell was obtained from the SEM images of the cross section of carbon foam. Then, the radius of the spherical void can be determined from the solidity of the foam. The Pro/Engineering®, modeling application software, was used to model the unit-cell and calculate the solid volume. In the present study, the unit-cell dimension c is taken as 1.8 mm and the solidity as 0.1312. The procedure for determining the Young's modulus and tensile strength of the solid carbon is as follows. The strength of the solid carbon in the foam can be easily estimated from the tensile strength of the carbon foam, which is measured experimentally. The relation between the foam tensile strength and the solid carbon strength is given by

$$\sigma_{us} = \sigma_u^* \frac{c^2}{A_{\min}} \quad \text{Eqn. 4}$$

where A_{\min} is the minimum cross sectional area of the struts in the carbon foam normal to the principal material axis. It should be noted that the tensile strength of the foam is for a direction parallel to one of the principal material axes. The area A_{\min} was obtained from the modeling software. Substituting the dimensions of the unit-cell and the measured carbon foam tensile strength ($\sigma_u^* = 3.58\text{MPa}$), the strength of solid carbon was estimated as 162 MPa. The Young's modulus E_s of solid carbon was estimated by a trial and error method. The unit-cell was modeled by using 4-noded tetrahedral solid elements. Due to symmetry only a portion of the unit-cell was modeled and periodic boundary conditions were imposed such that only one of the macro-strains is non-zero. We assume a value for E_s and ν_s and the forces required to deform the unit cell are calculated from the nodal reactions. From the forces the macro-stresses can be computed. For example

$$\sigma_x^* = \frac{\sum F_x}{c^2}, \quad \sigma_y^* = \frac{\sum F_y}{c^2} \quad \text{Eqn. 5}$$

The carbon foam is assumed as an orthotropic material and the macro-stresses and strains are substituted in the constitutive relation to obtain the compliance coefficients S_{ij} . From the S matrix the elastic constants can be estimated using the following relations:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1^* \\ \varepsilon_2^* \\ \varepsilon_3^* \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & S_{23} \\ S_{13} & S_{23} & S_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1^* \\ \sigma_2^* \\ \sigma_3^* \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{Eqn. 6}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_2} & -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_3} \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} & \frac{1}{E_2} & -\frac{\nu_{32}}{E_3} \\ -\frac{\nu_{13}}{E_1} & \frac{\nu_{23}}{E_2} & \frac{1}{E_3} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & S_{23} \\ S_{13} & S_{23} & S_{33} \end{bmatrix}$$

The FE model contained approximately 100,000 solid tetrahedral elements. A displacement $u_y=1$ was applied to the top surface of a unit cell (Fig. 6). The contour plot of maximum principal stresses is depicted in Fig. 6. For the sake of simplicity no attempt was made to estimate the Poisson's ratio ν_s using the micro-mechanical methods and it was assumed to be equal to 0.17 based on a previous study [2]. Based on the foam properties given in Table 1 and the unit-cell size c of 1.8mm, the Young's modulus of solid carbon E_s was estimated to be 2.6 GPa. Using this value for E_s the Young's modulus of carbon foams of various solidity was calculated using the FE model and they are shown in Fig. 8. The shear modulus was also calculated using the micromechanics analysis developed by Marrey and Sankar [5]. The variation of shear modulus as function of solidity is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 6 Boundary conditions on the unit-cell surfaces and maximum principal stress distribution when the unit-cell is stretched in the y-direction

Fig. 7 Boundary conditions on the unit-cell surfaces and maximum principal stress distribution when the unit-cell is under shear displacement

Beam Model: In addition to the solid model described in the preceding section a simple lattice model was also attempted. In this model the foam is assumed to be made up of struts arranged in a cubic lattice pattern. The length of the strut was equal to the unit-cell dimension. The struts were assumed to be of square cross section and their dimensions were determined from the solidity of the foam. The wall thickness h of carbon foam is determined by using the expression for relative density as follows [2]:

$$\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} = 3\left(\frac{h}{c}\right)^2 - 2\frac{h^3}{c^3} \quad \text{Eqn. 7}$$

From the equation above, the wall thickness h is determined to be 0.4086mm for a solidity of 0.1312 and $c = 1.8$ mm. Since this beam model is a simple one, FE methods are not necessary to determine the relation between the solid properties and foam properties. Analytical expressions for various elastic properties have been derived earlier [2], and the results are as follows:

$$E_s = \left(\frac{c}{h}\right)^2 E^* \quad \text{Eqn. 8}$$

$$G^* = \frac{1}{2} E_s \left(\frac{h}{c} \right)^4 \quad \text{Eqn. 9}$$

The relation between the strength of the foam (σ_u^*) and the solid strut strength (σ_{us}) is given by

$$\sigma_{us} = \left(\frac{c}{h} \right)^2 \sigma_u^* \quad \text{Eqn. 10}$$

Based on the Eqns. 8 and 9, the Young's modulus E_s and the strength σ_{us} are found to be 2.4MPa and 69.5MPa, respectively. The variation of E^* and G^* with the solidity for the beam model are shown, respectively, in Figs. 8 and 9.

Fracture toughness estimation using the solid model: In this section we describe a finite element based micromechanics model to estimate the fracture toughness of the cellular solid. The crack is assumed to be parallel to one of the principal material axes. To determine the fracture toughness a small region of the foam around the crack tip is modeled using finite elements. Only Mode I fracture is considered in the present study. The boundary of the cellular solid is subjected to displacement boundary conditions (u_x and u_y) corresponding to an arbitrary value of K_I . The displacement components in the vicinity of a crack tip in an orthotropic solid can be found in [5] and they are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} u_x &= K_I \sqrt{\frac{2r}{\pi}} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{1}{s_1 - s_2} \left[s_1 p_2 (\cos \theta + s_2 \sin \theta)^{1/2} - s_2 p_1 (\cos \theta + s_1 \sin \theta)^{1/2} \right] \right\} \\ u_y &= K_I \sqrt{\frac{2r}{\pi}} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{1}{s_1 - s_2} \left[s_1 q_2 (\cos \theta + s_2 \sin \theta)^{1/2} - s_2 q_1 (\cos \theta + s_1 \sin \theta)^{1/2} \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eqn. 11}$$

The parameters s_1 , s_2 , p_1 , p_2 , q_1 and q_2 depend on the orthotropic material constants [6]. The maximum tensile stress in the unit-cells is calculated from the FE model. In the case of three-dimensional solid model the maximum stress is obtained as an output of the FE program. From the result the value of K_I that will cause rupture of the strut is estimated, which then is taken as the fracture toughness of the cellular solid. The solid model used 42 cells with 135,000 solid tetrahedral elements as shown in Fig. 10. A contour plot of maximum principal stress is shown in Fig. 10. When unit K_I was applied to the crack tip, maximum principal stress was found equal to 1,463 Pa. Then the fracture toughness is obtained from the strength of the solid carbon ($\sigma_{us} = 0.162 \text{ MPa}$) as

$$K_{IC} = \frac{\sigma_{us}}{\sigma_{\max}} = \frac{162 \times 10^6}{1463} = 0.11 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{m} \quad \text{Eqn. 12}$$

Comparing Eqn. 12 with the results of fracture toughness experiments (Table 3), the difference is about 16%. One reason for the difference could be the small number of cells used in the FE simulation. The FE model was used to study the variation of fracture toughness with relative density and the resulting relationship is shown in Fig. 11. Gibson and Ashby [1] provided analytical results for fracture toughness for open-cell foam and their formula is given below:

$$\frac{K_{IC}^*}{\sigma_{us} \sqrt{\pi c}} = 0.65 \left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \right)^{3/2} \quad \text{Eqn. 13}$$

where σ_{us} is the tensile strength of the solid.

Fig. 10 Maximum principal stress distribution of solid and beam models for a unit K_I at the crack tip

Fracture toughness using the beam model: The procedure for simulating fracture using the beam model is same as that for the FE solid model. The beam model of carbon foam (Fig. 10) consisted of 10,000 cells using approximately 20,000 beam elements. When using the beam model the rotational degree of freedom at each node of the beam element on the boundary of the solid is left as unknown and no couples are applied at these nodes. The maximum principal stress distribution in the beam model is shown in Fig. 10. The maximum principal stress for a unit K_I was found to be equal to 506 Pa. Therefore, the fracture toughness can be estimated as

$$K_{IC} = \frac{\sigma_{us}}{\sigma_{\max}} = \frac{69 \times 10^6}{506} = 0.137 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{m} \quad \text{Eqn. 14}$$

The difference between the experimental result and that from the beam model is only 3%. The beam model was also used to study the variation of fracture toughness with the solidity and it is presented in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11 Variation of fracture toughness of carbon foam with relative density

CONCLUSION

Four point bend tests were performed on SENB specimens made of carbon foam, and their Mode I fracture toughness was measured. Two micro-mechanical models were developed to simulate Mode I fracture. Both models assumed a cube as the unit-cell of the foam. In the first model solid finite elements were used to model the foam. The measured density of the carbon foam was used in determining the void size in the micromechanical model. Young's modulus and tensile strength of the solid carbon were also determined from the corresponding values of the carbon foam measured experimentally. A small region surrounding the crack tip was modeled using finite elements. The crack was assumed parallel to one of the principal material directions. Boundary displacements were calculated using linear elastic fracture mechanics for orthotropic materials. From the FE simulation the stress intensity factor K_I that will cause the failure of the crack-tip elements was determined, and this was taken as the fracture toughness of the cellular material. Good agreement between FE and experimental results indicates that micromechanics simulations can be successfully used to study crack propagation in cellular solids. Future work will focus on mixed mode fracture and crack propagation at an angle to the principal material direction.

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REFERENCES

1. Gibson, L.J. and Ashby, M.F., *Cellular Solids: Structure and Properties*, Second Edition, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom, 1988.
2. Choi, S. and Sankar, B.V. "Micromechanical Methods to Predict the Fracture Toughness of Cellular Solids", *Technical Report*, Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, University of Florida, PO Box 116250, Gainesville, FL 32611, 2002.
3. Charles W. Fowlkes 'Fracture toughness tests of a rigid polyurethane foam', *International Journal of Fracture*, 1974, 10(1), pp. 99-108.
4. Hellan, K. *Introduction to Fracture Mechanics*, McGraw-Hill, NY, 1984, pp. 244
5. Marrey, Ramesh V. and Sankar, Bhavani V., "Micromechanical Models for Textile Structural Composites," NASA contractor report, 198229, October 1995.
6. Sih, G.C. and Liebowitz, H., "Mathematical Theories of Brittle Fracture," *Fracture-An Advanced Treatise*, Volume 2, Liebowitz, H., Ed., Academic Press, New York, 1968, pp. 67-190.